

NOTES

Studies in the Synthesis of Coumarino- α -Pyrones and Furocoumarins : Part III.*

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In order to study the relationship between structure and anti-coagulant activity of benzopyranyl (3,2-c) pyran-2, 8-diones and 4H furo (3, 2-c) benzopyran-4-ones, it was thought of interest to synthesise benzo (3, 4) benzopyranyl (3, 2-c) pyran-2, 8-dione (Ia) and its 10-methyl derivative (Ib) and degrade them respectively to 4H-furo (3, 2-c) benzo (6,7) benzopyranyl-4-one (IIa) and its 3-methyl derivative (IIb) according to the method developed by Trivedi and Sethna¹.

4-Hydroxy-5, 6-benzocoumarin on Pechmann condensation with malic acid in the presence of 80% sulphuric acid gave (Ia) which on bromination yielded its 9-bromo derivative (Ic). This bromo derivative on hydrolysis with 10% sodium carbonate solution afforded 4H-furo (3, 2-c) benzo (6, 7) benzopyranyl-4-one-2-carboxylic acid (IIc) which was decarboxylated to (IIa).

- Ia : R = R¹ = H
 b : R = CH₃ ; R¹ = H
 c : R = H ; R¹ = Br
 d : R = CH₃ ; R¹ = Br

- IIa : R = R¹ = H
 b : R = H ; R¹ = CH₃
 c : R = COOH ; R¹ = H
 d : R = COOH ; R¹ = CH₃

4-Hydroxy-5, 6-benzocoumarin on a similar condensation with ethyl acetoacetate gave 10-methyl benzo (3, 4) benzopyranyl (3, 2-c) pyran-2, 8-dione (Ib) as reported by Patell and Usgaonker². This on bromination gave the 9-bromo derivative (Id), which on hydrolysis with 10% sodium carbonate solution afforded 2-(o-hydroxy- α -naphthyl) -4-methyl furan-3-carboxylic acid (III) and not 3-methyl-4H-furo (3, 2-c)

* Part II, *This Journal*, 1966, 43, 804.

1. Trivedi and Sethna, *This Journal*, 1963, 40, 563.

2. Patell and Usgaonker, *This Journal*, 1966, 43, 536.

benzo (6, 7) benzopyranyl-4-one-2--carboxylic acid (II_d). The formation of (III) from the expected (II_d) is shown according to following route through the intermediate (IV), which could not be isolated.

The acid (III) was cyclised to (II_b) when refluxed with hydrochloric acid.

EXPERIMENTAL

Benzo (3,4) benzopyranyl (3, 2-c) pyran-2, 8-dione (Ia): A mixture of 4-hydroxy-5, 6-benzocoumarin (4 g) and malic acid (4 g) was heated on a steam bath with gradual addition of 80% sulphuric acid (40 ml) in 45 min. period. Heating was continued for further 4 hr. The reaction mixture was added to ice and the product filtered, washed with sodium bicarbonate solution, dried and crystallised from benzene in shining crystals, 310°. Yield 1 g. (Found: C, 72.38; H, 3.31. $C_{16}H_8O_4$ requires C, 72.73; H, 3.03%).

9-Bromo benzo (3, 4) benzopyranyl (3, 2-c) pyran-2, 8-dione (Ic): (Ia) (0.66 g) was dissolved in minimum amount of acetic acid and bromine, dissolved in acetic acid (9 ml; 20%; 4 mole) was added and the mixture heated on a water bath for 3 hr. The reaction mixture was then added to ice and the bromo derivative filtered, dried and crystallised from benzene m. p. 282°. Yield 0.5 g. (Found: Br, 23.68. $C_{16}H_7O_4Br$ requires Br, 23.32%).

4H-Furo (3,2-c) benzo (6, 7) benzopyranyl-4-one carboxylic acid (IIc): (Ic) (0.5 g) was mixed with sodium carbonate solution (10 ml; 10%) and was refluxed for 4 hr. The solution was allowed to cool and filtered. The filtrate on acidification gave the product which was crystallised from acetic acid in yellowish crystals, m.p. 318°. Yield 0.1 g. (Found: C, 68.47; H, 2.50. $C_{16}H_8O_5$ requires C, 68.57; H, 2.85%).

4H-Furo (3, 2-c) benzo (6, 7) benzopyranyl-4-one (IIa): (IIc) (0.4) was heated on a sand bath with quinoline (5 ml) and copper bronze (0.2 g) for 1 hr. The reaction mixture was filtered hot, acidified with hydrochloric acid and filtered again. The filtrate was diluted with water and extracted with ether. The product

obtained after evaporation of ether was washed with sodium bicarbonate solution and crystallised from dil. acetic acid in colourless needles, m.p. 181°. Yield 0.1 g. (Found : C, 76.51 ; H, 3.16. $C_{15}H_8O_8$ requires C, 76.27 ; H, 3.41%).

9-Bromo-10 methyl benzo (3, 4) benzopyranyl (3, 2-c) pyran-2, 8-dione (Id) : (Ib) (1.5 g) was dissolved in minimum amount of acetic acid and bromine dissolved in acetic acid (18 ml ; 20% ; 4 mole) was added slowly with constant stirring and the mixture was heated on a water bath for 3 hr. The compound separated was filtered, dried and crystallised from benzene in yellow shining needles, m.p. 235°. Yield 1 g. (Found : Br, 22.67 ; $C_{17}H_9O_4Br$ requires Br, 22.4%).

2-(o-Hydroxy- α -naphthyl)-4-methyl furan-3-carboxylic acid (III) : (Ic) (0.8 g) was refluxed with sodium carbonate solution (15 ml ; 10%) for 2 hr. The reaction mixture was allowed to cool, filtered and acidified. The product was purified by dissolving it in sodium carbonate solution reprecipitated and crystallised from hot water in colourless crystals, m.p. 182°. Yield 0.1 g. (Found : C 17.94 ; H, 4.75. $C_{16}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 71.61 ; H, 4.48%).

3-Methyl-4H-furo (3, 2-c) benzopyranyl-4-one (Iib) : *2-(o-Hydroxy- α -naphthyl)-4-methyl furo-3-carboxylic acid* (0.5 g) was dissolved in ethanol and refluxed with hydrochloric acid (5 ml) for 4 hr. The separated product was filtered and crystallised from acetic acid in shining needles, m.p. 247°. Yield 0.1 g. (Found : C, 74.72 ; H, 4.27. $C_{14}H_{10}O_8$ requires C, 74.33 ; H, 4.43%).

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